

Heterogeneous Embedded Neural Processing Units Utilizing PCM-based Analog In-Memory Computing

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Abstract— We propose an embedded Neural Processing Unit (NPU) architecture for deep learning inference to address the stringent energy, area, and cost requirements of edge AI. This heterogeneous architecture integrates a variety of digital and analog accelerator nodes to cater to diverse operation types and precision requirements. To achieve high energy efficiency while maintaining substantial non-volatile on-chip weight capacity, we utilize Analog In-Memory Computing (AIMC) tiles based on Phase-Change Memory (PCM) for Matrix-Vector Multiplications (MVMs). Additionally, a digital data path and a programmable software cluster facilitate end-to-end inference across multiple precision levels. The NPU is projected to deliver competitive throughput for transformer Neural Networks (NNs), rivaling high-end System-on-Chips (SoCs) for mobile devices and edge accelerators fabricated at more advanced technology nodes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The data intensive nature and highly parallel compute requirements of AI models lead to specialized Neural Processing Units (NPUs) being integrated on to System-on-Chip (SoC) devices for AI edge applications (Fig. 1). Typically, model weights are stored in external memory or on-chip Non-Volatile Memory (NVM). In-Memory Computing (IMC) can further reduce data movement by performing Matrix-Vector Multiplication (MVM) operations directly within customized memory arrays. Among the various forms of IMC, Digital IMC (DIMC) performs scalar multiplications of preloaded weights and activations close to the memory cells and performs the partial sum accumulation using digital adder trees [1]. On the other hand, Analog IMC (AIMC) exploits the inherent row parallelism of memory arrays by executing scalar multiplications and partial sum accumulations in the analog domain [2]. In comparison to DIMC, this approach offers the potential for higher density and lower power consumption. The most mature form of AIMC is based on SRAM technology [3],

with multi-bit weights encoded across multiple devices. However, AIMC based on embedded NVM cells presents a promising prospect for NPUs, offering increased on-chip weight density. Among various NVM technologies for AIMC, Phase-Change Memory (PCM) cells are particularly attractive. The analog storage capability and Back-End-Of-the-Line implementation enables high on-chip weight capacity (Figs. 2,3), while offering a scalability path to more advanced nodes. As embedded memory, PCM has already been proven in industrial settings [4,5]. Moreover, recent multi-tile PCM-based AIMC chips showcase the energy efficiency of MVM operations with sufficient computational precision [6,7].

An NPU architecture for edge applications needs to offer a high degree of flexibility and versatility. It should support various model mappings based on model weight size, required latency/throughput, and the available power budget. Furthermore, seamlessly integrating both analog and digital compute nodes with a high bandwidth communication fabric is crucial for effectively managing end-to-end tasks.

II. HETEROGENEOUS NPU

The NPU architecture comprises various nodes, in addition to the PCM-based AIMC tiles (Fig. 4). A Digital Processing Unit (DPU) serves as a programmable data path and can handle a large selection of operators including convolutions, pooling, arithmetic, and simple activation functions with 8-bit or 16-bit fixed-point precision. A software-programmable RISC-V cluster with shared scratchpad memory and a specialized tensor product data-path with fused multiply-accumulate units, complements the DPU in performing accuracy-critical operations in FP16 precision [8]. The DPU and the RISC-V coprocessor units constitute the digital accelerator nodes of the NPU. The Local Storage Unit (LSU) provides data manipulation operations and local SRAM-based storage. These nodes are connected through a 64-bit wide 2D mesh interconnect [9] with bit-parallel communication. A digital

wrapper is present at each node to interface the interconnect and to perform control tasks (Fig. 5). Borderguard circuits handle data routing between the interconnect and node FIFOs which are controlled by borderguard controllers operating on a basic instruction set. A stall controller regulates data communication based on data availability. A RISC-V-based local controller is responsible for the overall control flow within each node. An NPU configuration with 20 nodes is shown in Fig. 4, with an estimated area of $\sim 30 \text{ mm}^2$ on ST’s 28nm FD-SOI technology [4], operating at 500MHz with an estimated average power dissipation below 1W. This architecture is configurable at design time, allowing to scale effectively with varying computational demands (Fig. 6).

III. PCM BASED ON GE-GST

A Ge-GST-based PCM with a wall device architecture [4] is adopted, where an n-type MOSFET selector ensures precise control over the current flowing through the device during programming, thereby enabling analog weight storage. Tight conductance distributions are achieved for various conductance targets using a feedback-driven program-and-verify scheme (Fig. 7). Fig. 8 shows the drift and read noise behavior across more than 280 devices, programmed to various conductance states. While the state-dependent drift and read noise characteristics can be detrimental for inference accuracies over time scales exceeding 1 hour, this can be mitigated by using optimized device structures that show lower drift and read noise as depicted in Fig. 9.

IV. FLEXIBLE ANALOG TILE ARCHITECTURE

The AIMC tile supports a 512×512 MVM. It is physically organized in 4×4 local arrays of unit cells containing a total of 1,024 word-lines and 4,096 bit-lines (Fig. 10). Each unit cell contains up to 16 PCM devices. Positive and negative inputs are applied through separate word lines. The input precision is flexible, supporting both signed values (1-8 bits) and unsigned values (1-7 bits). The bit lines are connected to current-controlled oscillator-based ADCs [10] with a flexible switch mechanism (Fig. 11). Higher precision for weight representation can be achieved by connecting multiple bit-lines to an ADC. Conversely, connecting fewer bit-lines results in a larger weight capacity. Fig. 12 shows that the energy efficiency of the AIMC tile is expected to exceed recent macros [3,6] with a component-wise energy breakdown provided in Fig. 13. A compact digital post-processing unit based on fixed-point arithmetic performs affine scaling functions on the ADC output to address circuit mismatches and PCM non-idealities such as drift [11]. In addition, the unit supports partial sum and residual addition, batch-normalization, ReLU activation, and scaling of the AIMC tile outputs down to 8-bit precision.

V. LANGUAGE PROCESSING ON NPU

The NPU architecture supports a wide range of Neural Network (NN) models, including CNNs, LSTMs, and transformers. We will focus on the latter and study MobileBERT, which has 24 encoder layers with 4 attention heads. It requires over 20 million weight parameters trained for a question-answering task on the SQUAD v1.1 dataset. One

sample mapping of the model to an NPU with 20 nodes is shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 15 compares MobileBERT model throughput performance across a spectrum of systems from high-end mobile and laptop devices to low-power and low-cost edge devices. The NPU with 3 digital accelerator nodes is comparable in throughput to the Google Pixel 6 with EdgeTPU™ and provides better throughput than the ARM Ethos-U65™. Moreover, even with an average power budget below 1W and cost-effective 28nm technology, the NPU throughput with 5 digital accelerators approaches half that of some advanced high-end SoCs for laptop and mobile devices on advanced technology nodes for this benchmark. Due to the limited publicly available information on the energy and area efficiency of these devices, we focus solely on the throughput comparison. However, significant energy benefits are anticipated for the NPU, as all model weights are stored on the AIMC tiles, eliminating the need for off-chip weight loading during the MobileBERT runtime.

VI. ACCURACY STUDIES

The IBM Analog Hardware Acceleration Kit [15] is used to perform hardware-aware re-training of a floating-point pre-trained MobileBERT model, which achieves an F1-score of 90.02 on SQUAD v1.1 dataset [16]. The re-training was done for 15 epochs using additive noise injection on weights with a standard deviation of 6.7% using an ADAM optimizer and a cross-entropy loss with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-5} . During training, weights were clipped 3 standard deviations from the mean and an input/output quantization (8 bits) was performed. During inference, statistical PCM models for programming noise, drift, and read noise data extracted from device measurements were used. A global drift compensation mechanism is applied during inference [15]. Fig. 16 shows the temporal dependence of the F1 score over a period of one month, showing only marginal drop from the floating-point baseline with the optimized PCM device structure. The heterogeneity of the NPU architecture can be leveraged for higher F1 scores by assigning selected NN layers to higher precision compute resources. This is demonstrated in Fig. 17 where the designated layers are computed with floating-point precision without any further re-training.

VII. CONCLUSION

We propose a heterogeneous embedded NPU architecture for edge AI inference applications, where mix of analog and digital accelerator nodes are interconnected through a 2D mesh. The Ge-GST PCM-based AIMC tiles offer dense analog weight storage while the digital accelerator nodes support both low precision fixed-point and floating-point precision, allowing for versatile operation. An NPU with a $\sim 30 \text{ mm}^2$ area footprint on 28nm ST’s FD-SOI technology is expected to provide sufficient on-chip weight storage capacity for all the encoder weights of MobileBERT, with an average power dissipation below 1W. This NPU configuration is estimated to deliver competitive inference throughput for transformer NNs, approaching high-end SoCs for mobile devices.

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Fig. 1. Evolution of the Neural Processing Units (NPU) towards digital and analog in-memory computing.

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Fig. 2. PCM integration in ST 28nm FD-SOI technology.

Fig. 3. The analog storage capability of PCM through creation of different amorphous dome dimensions.

Fig. 4. The heterogeneous NPU architecture consisting of 20 nodes is shown. The nodes are interconnected with a 2D mesh-based communication fabric. The NPU is connected to the other system components through the AXI bus.

Fig. 6. The architecture is parametric and scalable at design-time, allowing to accommodate various target applications and use cases (1), (2), (3). Moreover, larger NPUs (2) or multiple NPUs (3) can be adopted in larger systems.

Fig. 5. Each NPU node consists of an accelerator (analog/digital) or a memory unit, integrated into a digital wrapper.

Fig. 7. Conductance distributions shown for six target states, obtained over 45 devices per state after 20 program-and-verify iterations with a precision of 5% around the programmed value.

Fig. 8. The drift coefficient and read noise as a function of the programmed conductance across 288 devices. Drift follows the relation $G(t) = G(t_0)(t/t_0)^{-\nu}$, where $G(t)$ and $G(t_0)$ denotes the conductances at time t and t_0 , respectively and ν is the drift coefficient.

Fig. 9. Drift and read noise distributions for 288 standard and 170 optimized PCM devices.

Fig. 10. PCM-based AIMC tile is organized in 16 local arrays. The maximum signed weight storage capacity per tile is 2.1M.

Fig. 11. A switching mechanism supports ADC multiplexing across PCM devices, or alternatively, multiple PCM devices can be combined for higher compute precision.

Fig. 12. Energy efficiency of the AIMC tile with 8-bit signed input and signed analog weights. α is the input and weight values relative to the maximum achievable input and weight values.

Fig. 13. Energy breakdown of the components, shown for read voltage of 30 mV and $\alpha = 0.2$ for signed inputs and signed weights.

Fig. 14. The MobileBERT operator mapping strategy shown here utilizes AIMC tiles for MVMs, where each of the 8 weight sets represent three encoder layer weights. Off-chip memory is used to store the embeddings.

Fig. 16. Mean and standard deviation of MobileBERT F1 score over 10 inference runs. MobileBERT accuracy target is defined as 93% of the FP implementation by MLPerf [12].

Devices	Domain	Node [nm]	Freq.[GHz]	Inf/s	Inf/s [scaled]**
ARM Ethos-U65™ *	Edge	16	1	6	4
NPU, 2 digital accelerators	Edge	28	0.5	15.3	15.3
NPU, 3 digital accelerators	Edge	28	0.5	29.3	29.3
NPU, 5 digital accelerators	Edge	28	0.5	51.6	51.6
Google Pixel 6, EdgeTPU™ [13]	Phones (High-end SoC)	5	Up to 2.8	66.7	29.7
Qualcomm Snapdragon X Elite, Hexagon™ [12]	Laptop (High-end SoC)	4	Up to 3.8	298.9	121.2
Exynos 2400, Samsung NPU [12]	Phones (High-end SoC)	4	Up to 3.2	317.1	128.5
Qualcomm Snapdragon 8 Gen 3, Hexagon™ [12]	Phones (High-end SoC)	4	Up to 3	433.3	175.7

* Using MobileBERT-EdgeTPU-XS-quant model obtained from [13]
 ** Technology scaling done in line with ST process insights and [14]

Fig. 15. MobileBERT throughput performance (sequence length 384) comparing edge platforms (targeting low energy consumption) with high-end SoCs (comprising significantly advanced computation capability e.g., multi-core CPUs, GPUs, accelerators, high-bandwidth memory interfaces such as LPDDR5, and large system cache). Ethos-U65 figures obtained from the Ethos toolchain selecting the 512 MAC/cycle NPU variant paired with 512KB SRAM in the 'Ethos_U65_High_End' system configuration [17].

Fig. 17. Mapping studies (10 inference runs, 1 day inference time) reveal the impact of computing each specific MVM-layer-type at FP precision. Other layer-types remain on AIMC tiles.